

Synthetic, structural and electrical studies of some polychelates derived from bis(mercaptoacetamido)-3,3'-dimethoxybenzidine

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The polychelates of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}-bis(mercaptoacetamido)dimethoxybenzidine (BMADMB) have been prepared. In these chelates, the ligand BMADMB exhibits bis-bidentate character and coordinates symmetrically with the metal through nitrogen of amido and sulfur of mercapto groups. Thermogravimetric studies indicate a two-stage decomposition. The thermodynamic parameters and the order of reactions have been calculated from the TG data and comparable values are obtained. D.C. electrical conductivity of all the chelates have also been measured over 303–403 K range.

The facile regenerability, higher stability and operational flexibility of the coordination polymers has created considerable research interest in recent years¹. The formation of a macromolecular chain may be expected for bis-ligand with two chelating sites which for steric reasons cannot interact with the same metal ion². Keeping this view in mind we have synthesized the bidentate double-faced ligand bis(mercaptoacetamido)dimethoxybenzidine (BMADMB) and its polychelates with bivalent Mn, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, and Cd ions. The thermal and electrical properties of the polychelates have been studied.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis data of the polychelates (Table 1) indicate 1 : 1 metal : ligand stoichiometry which is further confirmed with the help of TG analysis. All the polychelates are coloured amorphous solid, air-stable, and insoluble in water and common organic solvents. The in-

solubility of these polychelates in water and organic solvents indicates their polymeric nature³.

The IR spectra of polymeric chelates do not significantly differ from each other but they do differ from that of the ligand in certain characteristic frequencies. The ligand band at 3330 cm⁻¹ (NH) shifted to lower wavenumbers by about 20 cm⁻¹ in the metal chelates indicating coordination of amido nitrogen to the metal ion. The ligand band at 1620 cm⁻¹ (C=O) remained undisturbed in the metal chelates, indicating the non-coordination of oxygen atom in the ligand. The fairly strong ligand band at 2600 cm⁻¹ (SH) disappeared in the spectra of the chelates, indicating involvement of SH group in the coordination⁴. The band at 1240 cm⁻¹ is attributed to Ar–O–CH₃⁵. The far-IR spectral data of polychelates showed bands at 410–560 (M–N) and 340–360 cm⁻¹ (N–S)⁶. These bands are not observed in the spectrum of the ligand.

Table 1. Electrical conductivity and thermal data of the polychelates*

Compd.	Decomp. temp. °C	σ $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ (373 K)	E_a eV	Activation energy**		$-\Delta S$ J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔF kJ ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$-S^*$ kJ K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	Z S^{-1}	Ord. of react. n
				FC	SW					
[Mn ^{II} (BMADMB).2H ₂ O] _n	370	1.21×10^{-6}	1.53	32.82	30.74	295.04	122.20	207.19	210.73	0.90
[Co ^{II} (BMADMB).2H ₂ O] _n	260	3.76×10^{-4}	1.20	28.72	28.45	296.63	121.56	205.76	265.55	0.90
[Ni ^{II} (BMADMB).2H ₂ O] _n	390	1.29×10^{-6}	1.18	33.07	31.91	303.60	122.02	206.39	228.75	0.75
[[Cu ^{II} (BMADMB)] _n .H ₂ O]	310	6.09×10^{-1}	1.12	28.24	26.32	298.21	121.58	211.44	128.23	0.90
[Zn ^{II} (BMADMB)] _n	380	5.15×10^{-9}	1.09	36.16	35.90	297.11	126.19	208.35	208.23	0.75
[Cd ^{II} (BMADMB).2H ₂ O] _n	320	2.68×10^{-4}	0.80	38.29	38.29	275.56	122.47	201.85	495.36	0.55

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and metal analyses.

** FC = Freeman-Carroll; SW = Sharp-Wentworth.

The diffuse reflectance spectrum of the Mn^{II} polychelate exhibited three bands at 16722, 17123 and 19230 cm⁻¹ attributed to the transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} (G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g} (G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}, {}^4E_g (G)$, respectively, in support of an octahedral stereochemistry around Mn^{II} ion. The magnetic moment value of the Mn^{II} polychelate is 5.19 B.M. The lower value may be due to spin-exchange in solid state. The Co^{II} polychelate showed bands at 16583, 19120 and 23314 cm⁻¹ assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} (F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g} (F)$, ${}^4T_{1g} (F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} (P)$ and CT transitions, respectively, in an idealized octahedral stereochemistry supported by the observed magnetic moment (5.76 B.M.), which is in the range for high-spin octahedral complex⁷. The reflectance spectra of the Ni^{II} polychelate showed three bands at 10250, 16949 and 23255 cm⁻¹ due to spin-allowed transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g} (F)$, ${}^3A_{2g} (F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} (F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (P)$, respectively, indicating octahedral geometry around Ni^{II} ion⁸. This is further supported by the magnetic moment value of 2.75 B.M. The diffuse reflectance spectrum of the Cu^{II} polychelate showed two bands at 16583 and 19047 cm⁻¹, a diagnostic of a square-planar geometry. The possible assignments for these bands are ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$, respectively. The observed magnetic moment (1.70 B.M.) close to spin-only value suggests that the orbital contribution is almost quenched by the crystal field⁹. The Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} polychelates are diamagnetic as expected.

The TG analysis indicates that the polychelates decompose in a two-stage process after the loss of water molecules. The elimination of lattice and coordinated water molecules takes place first. In the present study, the polychelates of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cd^{II} showed mass-loss in the range 140–200° equal to 6.12% (7.47% calcd.), 6.75% (7.41% calcd.), 6.40% (7.11% calcd.) and 5.91% (6.68% calcd.), respectively, which may be due to the presence of two coordinated water molecules per repeating units of polychelates¹⁰. Thereafter, the non-coordinated part of the ligand is decomposed followed by the decomposition of actually coordinated chromophore residue¹¹. Above 690°, TG curves attain a constant level corresponding to the metal oxides. In case of the Cu^{II} polychelate, weight-loss at about 130° equal to 4.00% (3.81% calcd.) corresponds to one lattice water molecule¹². The decomposition is complete at 720° forming CuO. The anhydrous Zn^{II} polychelate is stable upto 220° and thereafter the organic part starts decomposing partially. Then there is an inflexion at 540° and gradual mass-loss is observed leading to the formation of ZnO. In the Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} polychelates, there is small increase in weight of the residue in the temperature range 400–740°, which may be due to the for-

mation of metal sulfide and sulfate in the course of decomposition at certain temperature¹³.

From the procedural decomposition data, the order of thermal stability was found to be Ni > Zn > Mn > Cd > Cu > Co. The Freeman-Carroll¹⁴ and Sharp-Wentworth¹⁵ methods have been used to evaluate various kinetic parameters such as activation energy and order of reaction and thermodynamic parameters such as entropy change (ΔS), free energy change (ΔF), apparent entropy (S^*) and frequency factor (Z) from the TG data. The values of the thermodynamic parameters (Table 1) are nearly the same for each chelates. This similarity indicates that the basic steps involved are similar in the thermal degradation of the polychelates. The low values of Z indicate that the decomposition reaction of the polychelates can be classified as slow reaction¹⁶. The negative values of ΔS indicate that the activated complex has more ordered structure than the reactants, and the reactions are slower than normal. It is also observed that the degradation of polymer is a complex process as noted from the non-integer order of reaction (n).

In the electrical domain, the temperature dependence of electrical conductivity obeys the equation¹⁷: $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(-E_a/kT)$, where σ_0 is a constant, E is the activation energy and k the Boltzmann constant. The values are given in Table 1. The plots of $\log \sigma$ vs $1/T$ for all the polychelates are found to be linear over the temperature range 323–403 K, indicating their semiconducting nature¹². The electrical conductivity of the chelate polymers increases in the order: Zn < Mn < Ni < Cd < Co < Cu at 100°. The values of activation energy lie in the range 0.80–1.53 eV, the higher value may be due to higher molecular weight of the ligand and its polychelate considering one unit. The results that electrical conductivity and activation energy of conduction of these polychelates vary with the metal ion, which may be explained on the basis of the influence of different metal ions in the polymer which increases the ionization tendency¹⁸.

Experimental

All the metal acetates and chloride used were of A.R. grade. Solvents were used after distillation.

Synthesis of ligand BMADMB: A mixture of mercaptoacetic acid (0.2 mol) in methanol (25 ml) and a few drops of H₂SO₄ (as a catalyst) was refluxed for ~30 min on a water-bath. Then 3,3'-dimethoxybenzidine (0.1 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) was added to it and refluxed for 3 h. The contents were extracted with ice-cold water, filtered and washed with hot water. The solid product was crystallised from ethanol, (yield 61%), m.p. 80°.

Synthesis of polychelates General method : Metal acetate (Cd^{II} chloride) and ligand BMADMB were dissolved in minimum quantity (20–30 ml) of DMF separately in 1 : 1 molar ratio. Both the solutions were filtered, mixed in hot condition and refluxed on an oil-bath for 5 h. The colored solid products obtained with different metals were washed with DMF and absolute ethanol followed by acetone and dried in vacuum dessicator over calcium chloride. The coordination polymers were found to be insoluble in water and most of the organic solvents and hence normal methods of characterisation such as NMR and electronic spectra could not be applied.

The metal content was determined by standard methods¹⁹. C and H analyses were performed at Microanalytical Section, C.D.R.I., Lucknow, while N and S were estimated by standard methods¹⁹. The magnetic susceptibility was determined by Gouy's method at room temperature. Diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded on a photoacoustic spectrophotometer (PAS) using BaSO₄ as calibrant and IR spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out on a TGS-2 Perkin-Elmer thermobalance at a heating rate of 10° per min in air. D.C. electrical conductivity was measured by voltage drop method using d.c. microvoltmeter in pellet form²⁰.

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